

A Spectrophotometric Determination of 2,4,5-Trichlorophenoxyacetic Acid

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MANY methods based on tlc¹, hplc², gas chromatography³ and colourimetry⁴ are reported for 2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4,5-T), an important herbicide and defoliant⁵. In the present communication, a spectrophotometric method based on the determination of formaldehyde which is obtained by the oxidation of 2,4,5-T with concentrated H₂SO₄ with J-acid to produce a blue dye in acidic medium is described.

Experimental

A Carl Zeiss Spekol spectrophotometer was used. Analytical grade chemicals were used. A stock solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) of 2,4,5-T was prepared in concentrated H₂SO₄ and a working standard solution (80 µg ml⁻¹) was prepared by appropriate dilution. A 0.4% solution of J-acid (6-amino-1-naphthol-3-sulphonic acid; Wilson) in concentrated H₂SO₄ was used.

Procedure 1 To an aliquot of standard solution containing 30–320 µg of 2,4,5-T dissolved in concentrated H₂SO₄ was added J-acid solution (1 ml) and the solution was kept in an oven (130–35°) for ~20 min. The contents of the test tube were allowed to attain room temperature and then poured dropwise into 50% ammonium acetate solution (25 ml) kept in an ice-bath. The blue coloured dye (pH ~2) produced was measured at 610 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Beer's law was obeyed in the range 30–320 µg of 2,4,5-T in 25 ml of final volume. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were 18.36 × 10³ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.074 µg cm⁻² respectively. The reproducibility of the method was checked by analysing 80 µg/25 ml of 2,4,5-T for a period of 8 days. The S.D. and R.S.D. were found to be ±0.012 and ±5.44% respectively for 8 determinations.

In order to assess validity of the present method, the effects of other pesticides and foreign species commonly present in water along with 2,4,5-T were studied. The tolerance limits (in µg) for foreign species in 80 µg/25 ml are as follows: phenyl mercury acetate (2100); carbaryl, propoxur (4000 each); kelthane (10000); DDT, BHC (2000 each); dimethionate (3000); parathion, malathion (2500 each); K⁺, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Mg^{II}, sulphate, nitrate, chloride (2000 each). 2,4-D had positive interference.

Application: To check the recovery, known amounts of 2,4,5-T was added to different samples. The polluted water and plant material samples were extracted with carbon tetrachloride (2 × 20 ml) and rice sample with ethanol (2 × 20 ml). Solvents were evaporated off under reduced pressure and 2,4,5-T was determined by the proposed method. Recoveries ranging from 90 to 98% were obtained.

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